

LifeWatch-ERIC Pilot Node

Advancing biodiversity and ecosystem science through EOSC

FACTSHEET FOR: Researchers; Students; Research organisations

Pilot Node Profile

LifeWatch ERIC is a European Research Infrastructure providing e-Science research facilities for investigating biodiversity and ecosystem functions. Its main focus is to enable data-driven, reproducible, and collaborative research.

Within EOSC Beyond, it integrates its services into a Pilot Node to improve the interoperability, discoverability and accessibility of environmental data and services across Europe.

Pilot Core Services

- **AAI**
Federated login to access services {production}
- **LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue**
Discovery of relevant resources {production}
- **Helpdesk**
User support {beta}

Pilot Exchange Services

- **LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue**
(data and service discovery)

EOSC Beyond Core Innovation Sandbox

A pre-production environment where a large range of users, from researchers to node operators, can test the latest developments of the EOSC core.

It acts as a Federator Node offering Core Federating Capabilities for the Pilot Nodes.

User story at-a-glance

As a Researcher, I need access to diverse biodiversity datasets and tools, but it's hard to find and connect them all.

Persona: Ecologist studying alien species distribution across different ecosystems

Goal: To access harmonised biodiversity datasets and relevant services, while also being able to execute those services.

Before: Executing a service demanded understanding complex technical details and manual setup.

After: Through the EOSC Beyond Discovery Hub, the researcher can now discover and access biodiversity datasets and services within a single environment. Federation with the EGI Node enables the researcher to execute services within an integrated EOSC ecosystem.

Benefit: Faster, easily accessible, and collaborative research workflows that support large-scale ecological analyses across Europe.

LifeWatch-ERIC Node integrations with the Core Innovation Sandbox and other Pilot Nodes

Integrated Core Federating Capabilities from the Core Innovation Sandbox

- AAI: federated login to access services (production)
- Discovery Hub: discovery of relevant resources (production)
- Deployment Service: provisioning of computational environment (production)
- HelpDesk: user support (production)
- Order Management: request and execution of services (PoC)

Integrated services from other Pilot Nodes

- EGI Cloud Compute (computing)

Value of the Node piloting activities

The LifeWatch ERIC Pilot Node demonstrates how biodiversity and ecosystem research services can be effectively federated within EOSC.

By integrating LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue with EOSC, the pilot enhances data discoverability, interoperability and cross-domain data and services used for environmental research.

This integration allows researchers to combine biodiversity datasets, services, and computational resources from multiple EOSC Nodes, fostering collaborative and reproducible science.

The pilot also contributes to defining the technical and procedural requirements for future environmental Nodes joining EOSC, providing a model for this kind of federation.

Next steps

The next phase will focus on extending the integration of LifeWatch services with additional EOSC Core components and validating the complete workflow execution chain.

Further testing will address interoperability across Nodes, while documentation and user feedback will guide the scaling of the LifeWatch Pilot to support more biodiversity and ecosystem research services.

About EOSC Beyond

www.eosc-beyond.eu

The ambition of EOSC Beyond is to support the growth of the EOSC in terms of integrated providers and active users by providing new Core technical solutions that allow developers of scientific application environments to easily compose a diverse portfolio of EOSC Resources, offering them as integrated capabilities to researchers.

Useful Links

LifeWatch-ERIC Pilot Node:

<https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/pilot/lifewatch-eric>

LifeWatch-ERIC:

<https://www.lifewatch.eu/>

LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue:

<https://metadatalogue.lifewatch.eu/srv/eng/catalog.search#/home>

